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International Innovation as the context for engineering education

A. Albuquerque de Souza Daneluz

Lecturer Mechanical Engineering
Fontys University of Applied Sciences
Eindhoven, the Netherlands
E-mail: a.albuquerqueDESOUZA@fontys.nl

A. Friesel

Professor DTU Diplom
Technical University of Denmark
Ballerup, Denmark
E-mail: anfri@dtu.dk

H. Geraedts

Senior Lecturer Mechanical Engineering
Fontys University of Applied Sciences
Eindhoven, the Netherlands
hgm.geraedts@fontys.nl

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INTRODUCTION

1 GENERAL

There is a growing awareness within European education that learning, innovation skills is a requirement in order to prepare engineering students for their future career in developing creative and innovative technological solutions.

Some of innovation skills are: the ability to function in international teams (to which communication skill is key), the ability to interact with people from other cultures, and the ability to work in interdisciplinary teams. This paper describes a common innovation engineering project, developed for students from Technical University of Denmark (DTU Diplom), Denmark, and students from Fontys University of Applied Sciences, Eindhoven, The Netherlands. The collaboration of engineering students in such project is vital to their education, as it provides them with the international setting, very similar to what they will face when working on innovation development in companies. The goal of the project was to prepare engineering students to excel on their innovation skills. The aim of this paper is to present different aspects of how innovation skills are being developed, within the context of an international innovation engineering project. The following items are described in this paper:

- The Key Role of Humanities in Innovation Engineering.
- Required Competencies in Innovation Engineering.
- Best Didactics to Create a Learning Environment in Innovation Engineering.
- Setting and Main Findings on Current DTU-Fontys Innovation Engineering Project.
- Lessons Learnt and Future Developments.

2 THE KEY ROLE OF HUMANITIES IN INNOVATION ENGINEERING

2.1 Innovation concept

Different stakeholders have different perceptions of what an innovation is. For some, it is a process of finding a creative new idea. For others, it is a research for a market opportunity. It is paramount to have a common perception on what innovation is as in company processes, innovations are developed from a market pulling side as well as from a technology pushing side, but there are also several other aspects that influence the process.

Humanities as the Determining Factor

Innovations are made by people, to people who have needs and wishes. It sounds logical but often the role of Humanities, here understood as the study of how humanity processes the human experience (via arts, history, philosophy, language, etc.) [2], is neglected. Humanities is the driving force, the determining factor in innovation engineering as it explains the causes, motivations, needs, and wishes of people. Therefore, when properly studied, Humanities provides not only the background to an innovation, but it also enables innovative engineers to assess the ethical impact of their innovations in society.

3 REQUIRED COMPETENCES IN INNOVATION ENGINEERING

3.1 What competences and why?

A variety of competencies is required from an engineer in order to fully develop innovation. Creativity and awareness, for example, are known to be key driving competencies but have already been developed elsewhere, e.g. in literature e.g. in

literature [3,4]. For the purpose of this article, however, an exclusive set of competencies called the **i⁵**-competencies will be presented, see Fig 1, as the competencies an innovation engineer must have:

Fig. 1. Competences of an Innovation Engineer.

1. Think and Act Intra/entrepreneurially: think independently, intuitively and in a consumer-friendly way. Take calculated risks, take responsibility, and foster a network in order to maximise corporate opportunities.
2. Develop Innovation: incorporate different relevant aspects in the process of product and process innovation. The development of innovative products requires that engineers acquire basic knowledge on ethics, patents as well as appropriate methodological approaches on designing.
3. Cooperate Interdisciplinary: cooperate with other disciplines. Face the opportunities and challenges of other disciplines, while recognising opportunities and challenges of one's own discipline, and effectively employing this mutual set of unique capabilities in teams. Modern technologies are also typically interdisciplinarily and involve the combination of knowledge and technologies from several fields.
4. Connect Inter-culturally: cooperate respectfully with different cultures, establish and maintain international contacts, and identify the relevance of the opportunities of several cultural environments in developing innovation. In an increasingly globalized world, engineers need international experiences to be able to communicate with customers and project partners all across the globe and to respect the cultural differences in order to maximise the possibilities of innovation.
5. Have Interpersonal skills: To possess certain leadership capacities, to be able to set up discussions with peers, to analyse the best choice, to use convincing reasoning, to be able to be a chairperson in meetings, to use project management methodologies, and to be an efficient team player. Interpersonal skills include also advanced knowledge about ethics and communication within teams, whether in a company environment or in relation to customers.

4 LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN INNOVATION ENGINEERING

4.1 The learning environment (Introduction to Project Collaboration DTU-Fontys)

The collaboration to develop an innovation engineering project for students from Technical University of Denmark (DTU Diplom) and Fontys University of Applied Sciences in Eindhoven was firstly effective in September 2017, but preparations were on the way around a year prior to that. The aim was to provide a learning environment in which, besides main stream engineering and technological knowledge, also international skills, communication skills, humanities overall knowledge, ethics, and cultural awareness were developed. Within the project, there was an ongoing effort to expose engineering students to challenges such as:

- Different professional cultures, as students in Mechanical Engineering and also from Marketing programs from Eindhoven work together with students in programs in Electronics and Software Engineering program from DTU.
- Different nationalities/cultures (Danish, Dutch, Brazilian and Polish)
- Communication only in English, as being non-native language for all students
- Differences in academic demands and calendars
- Working together as a team while maintain geographical distance
- Communication via email, phone and other electronic media

This is the setting which sharpens required skills to innovative engineers as engineering students are expected to develop themselves in unfamiliar areas. They are required to broaden their worldview and abilities, by embracing and acting upon a complete new set of circumstances. The place of curiosity, risk, mistake, cooperation, vulnerability and discovery becomes therefore paramount to the innovation engineering learning environment.

At the start, students were given information about the project. Teachers of Eindhoven and Denmark needed to find proper themes where each student of each discipline could use their different capabilities in a common project. Students had to find an invention that could lead to an interesting innovation for a company. However, Educational programs from Eindhoven and Copenhagen have different educational agendas, which became another pressing issue for the project. Thus, although project started in September 2017, only in October 2017 students from Copenhagen visited Eindhoven students. The three days visit, allowed for them to know each other and start growing into a real team. Following that visit, students worked on finding interesting inventions and, in collaboration with Marketing students, they investigated possibilities for their invention to become an innovation that could be marketable and, whereof, a business plan was set up. In January 2018, the Dutch students went to Copenhagen and together with their Danish counterparts presented their final results to the teaching staff of Copenhagen and Eindhoven. Students developed an inflatable compression stocking for people with circulatory problems. Usually, people with this difficulty need to wear elastic stockings, which are hard to put on, especially for elderly people, because it requires the help of

nurses to put on these stockings. An inflatable compression stocking does not require help from others and make a person more independent, this could be an interesting innovation for companies.

4.2 How to develop Key Competencies

There are different factors, described in literature, which help international and interdisciplinary teams to function [6,7 and 10]. They include various levels of technical expertise, motivation, social skills, but also cultural norms and expectations of team members. Teachers need to investigate and facilitate for students to understand a variety of cultural values in different countries, which is very important for teams to successfully accomplish their project. This facilitation includes, for example, the analysis of specific cultural behaviour of team members in terms of:

- the tradition of working individually or collectively in teams;
- leadership behaviours and patterns; norms for communication and interaction, direct or indirect communication;
- obstacles due to inadequate language or cultural skills.

The learning of competences cannot be obtained out of a book. Competences are complex structures of knowledge, skills, attitude and experiences. Students need to be given as real as possible environments in which they can experience what it means to act according to a certain competence. These real environments can be provided in different levels by applying appropriated mixed approach didactics. For this project, Copenhagen and Eindhoven educational programs employed different didactical approaches: a combination of lecturing, discussing groups and self-learning elements were used. However, an international innovation project-based context has been set as it provides the best conditions to learn engineering by experiencing it. Based on the five basic innovation competences mentioned in chapter 3, a realistic project was setup for students from DTU and Fontys. Students could experience the process of developing an innovation that can be used entrepreneurially, within a working context that was interdisciplinary and intercultural.

5 SETTING AND MAIN FINDINGS

5.1 Danish-Dutch Innovation Engineering Project Collaboration

Undergraduate engineering education, in many countries, has as one of the goals to prepare the engineering students to work with practical engineering tasks, improving company's products by innovations and even with technological inventions [5]. At the same time, many companies work globally and need engineers with abilities and skills to work in international teams, with engineers and technicians from other countries and cultures [6,7,8]. The industry in Europe and European Union supports international cooperation amongst universities in order to train students' skills to work in multicultural and interdisciplinary teams. Combining innovation based projects with international teamwork, significantly contributes to develop students' skills [9,10] in areas which also include communication skills in English, for example. These were

the main reasons for us to start our cooperation, the cooperation between DTU and Fontys, with the common project: International Collaborative Innovation Project. A student who has met the objectives of this common course/project will be able to:

- Function effectively in multidisciplinary teams;
- Perform with successful project planning;
- Take a project from design requirements to final working proof of concept;
- Synthesize, integrate and apply technical engineering course content to a real-world engineering project;
- Apply creativity in the design of systems, components, or processes;
- Ability to assess how Invention adds value to society by understanding people-planet-profit aspects.
- Communicate effectively in a multicultural, multidisciplinary way.
- Interact with and collaborate on a joint project with students from a different culture/nationality.

Overall content of course/project is: Project Management and Ethics; International/Intercultural and Interdisciplinary Teamwork; Planning, Designing and Implementing Technical Engineering Knowledge to a real-world engineering project, and Verbal and Written Communication with team members from other cultures and nationalities.

5.2 Main findings: Students Account on Innovation Engineering Project

The cooperation between DTU and Fontys run for the first time in fall semester 2017, and after 6 weeks of work (during the DTU students visit to Fontys Eindhoven) a survey was conducted in order to uncover students overall perceptions. Main findings are listed in Table 1:

Question	Students' answer
What are the most positive aspects you have experienced, up to now from the common project?	<p>We've got a bigger picture/knowledge on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International engineering and education • Other country's culture • Contacts with students from abroad • How to cooperate from a distance • Differences in teaching and programs at other universities • Interdisciplinary problems and challenges • How to deal with real-world engineering tasks/problems • That marketing is an important part of engineering projects • That communication with all team members is very important
What are the most negative experiences you have from the project?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time schedule must be decided very early • Difficulties to communicate because of misunderstanding of professional communicating language and English • Lack of personal contact, face-to-face meeting has to be solved at the very beginning of the project • It was difficult to find the proper idea for common project
What is needed for successful	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding the proper interdisciplinary project to work on • Making a time schedule and plan for the project early in the

cooperation and project work?	<p>process for students in DK and NL with exact same requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project which motivates both groups of students (mechanical and electronics/software) to work efficiently • Money to have the possibility to buy materials necessary to develop the product • Manual and/or template given by supervisors for project plan and schedule
Is there any cultural obstacle you experienced?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dutch students work more directly, and want, from the beginning, to decide specific tasks • Danish students want to investigate all possibilities and discuss all students' wishes • Different expectations, especially in the beginning, according to which day to communicate (differences in week schedule and other courses) and how often we should have Skype-meetings
What can be done better to plan visits?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination and whole plan of the visit in NL. It should be students' task and approved afterwards by supervisors/teachers

Table. 1. Questions and answers of students on their experience of the project.

6 CONCLUSION: LESSONS LEARNT AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

6.1 Usefulness for Society, Students and Companies

It has been highlighted at the first edition of the innovation engineering collaboration project that society and companies must and can play a bigger role in the project. Nonetheless, students were consumed by the intense demand the project set upon them and, for that, perhaps they were unable to fully develop the experience the project aims to provide them with. For the coming years, efforts will be put not only so that society and companies have a bigger saying, but also that they equally benefit from the project as main stakeholders. Concerning students, it has been learnt that regarding to team work, there has to be a better understanding of each other's cultural behaviour, which directly affects communication amongst team members. These two areas require further improvements.

6.2 Required Improvements on Project execution Approach

Students have pointed out that, at least, two face-to-face meetings (part of a visit to each other's universities), followed by a social gathering (for example a dinner), are very interesting to bind teams together and to better understand each other's cultures. Perhaps, another possibility is the development of a template with which students can set up a communication plan. Cards on which basic rules of communication will be written can possibly be adopted in order to support students to develop in an effective manner. For most of the students, the international project was the first time they encountered what it means to execute an internationally co-operation project. Although students were given enough information to start up their project, they were not fully capable to organize a smooth collaboration process. Cultural differences and differences in the timetables of each university were causing delay in schedules. In addition, it was seen that students were not using meetings in a professional way. This implies that it is important that universities help students to

start up their collaboration, by giving helpful templates and instructions. Lastly, it was observed that meeting personally, at the beginning of the project, adds tremendous value to the entire process.

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